

TRANSIENT WAVES IN A LAMINATED COMPOSITE PLATE TO A POINT EXCITATION

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SUMMARY: A new quadrature technique is presented to modify the Hybrid Numerical Method (HNM) proposed by the authors earlier for analyzing transient waves in anisotropic laminated plates excited by a time-step point source. In the modified HNM, eigen-frequencies and modal factor functions for wave modes are discretized instead of the discretization of the whole integrand of a Fourier inverse integral. In each rectangular sub-range, the eigen-frequencies and modal factor functions are replaced by planes, and the inverse Fourier integrations are then carried out analytically. The proposed modification can significantly reduce the sampling points in the inverse integrations. The modified HNM is much more efficient than the original HNM, and can be used to compute not only near field and short time responses but also far field and long time responses of anisotropic laminated plates without an increase in sampling points. Numerical examples are presented to demonstrate the modified HNM.

KEYWORDS : Wave Propagation, Elastic Wave, Composite Material, Laminate, Numerical Analysis, Fourier Transform, Numerical Quadrature

INTRODUCTION

Problems for wave propagation in composite materials are receiving increasing interest, since composite materials are widely used in modern industries. Wave propagation problems are related to many important areas such as applications of ultrasonic techniques, elastodynamics of structure as well as modern seismological interests.

Methods for analyzing elastodynamic responses of a plate may be summarized into three categories. The first category includes methods based on approximate quasi-static and thin plate theories [1-4]. These methods are useful for low-velocity impacts. The second category includes methods based on exact theories of elasticity, such as methods for responses in the time domain [5-8], and methods for responses in the frequency domain [9-12]. Of course results obtained in the frequency domain can be transformed into the time domain using Fourier transform techniques. One important advantage of the exact methods is the feasibility

for responses of high frequency. The third category is methods involving finite element techniques, such as methods in the time domain [13-15] and methods in the frequency domain [16-20]. These methods are suitable for responses in low to intermediate range of frequencies.

In studying the existing works, it is found that most of them have been done for isotropic media, and some of them for anisotropic media. For isotropic media, most of the works were dealing with three dimensional (3-D) problems, and for anisotropic media, many were for 2-D problems. Moreover, very few works have been done for anisotropic laminated plate with many layers subjected to a point load (3-D). This is because it is very difficult to obtain the responses of the plate to a point load. There are two major difficulties. One is due to the large number of interfaces in the thickness direction of the plate. These interfaces result in too much reflections and refractions of waves. Another difficulty is due the anisotropy of the material. The responses of the plate depend on the direction, and the problem cannot be treated as a two dimensional one as for isotropic cases. Hence, the computing time could be considerably large.

To the best knowledge of the authors, there are two pieces of work done for anisotropic plates subjected to a point load. One is the recent work by Mal and Lih [11] for a single layer anisotropic plate. This work has been done in the frequency domain by introducing material damping in order to overcome the singularity in an inverse Fourier integration. A technique has been presented to handle a 2-D irregular integration. Another piece of work has been done by Liu et al. [15] for multi-layered anisotropic plates subjected to a point load. A hybrid numerical method (HNM) has been proposed to obtain the responses in the time domain directly. In the HNM, the FEM and the fast Fourier transform techniques (FFT) are combined to obtain a high efficiency. Responses of anisotropic laminated plates [15] and for anisotropic functionally gradient piezoelectric plates [13] subjected to line and point loads have been efficiently computed. The advantages of the HNM are reducing memory storage in the computation and the efficiency in obtaining the whole wave fields on planes parallel to the plate plane. The disadvantage is that too much sampling points in the wavenumber domain is needed to obtain accurate results in the spatial domain especially for the far field and long time responses.

The objective of this paper is to overcome the disadvantage of the HNM and to improve the efficiency and the accuracy of the HNM for analyzing 3-D responses of multi-layered anisotropic plates. A new quadrature technique is suggested to evaluate the integration in the inverse Fourier transform. This technique can significantly reduce the sampling points in the evaluation of the integration. The modified HNM is much more efficient than the original HNM, and can be used to compute not only near field and short time responses but also far field and long time 3-D responses for anisotropic laminated plates without an increase in the sampling points. Examples to demonstrate the modified HNM are presented.

BASIC FORMULATION FOR THE HNM

Figure 1 shows a laminated plate with any number of anisotropic layers. The plate with a thickness of H is subjected to a point load, and the wave field excited by the point load is of interest in this paper. In the original HNM [15], the wave field in the plate is analyzed by following steps.

- The plate is first divided into N plate elements in the thickness direction.
- A set of approximate partial differential equations for an element is obtained by using the principle of the virtual work.

- By assembling the differential equations of all the elements, a set of partial differential equations for the whole plate is then obtained.
- These partial differential equations are with respect to the time t and the coordinates x and y , which define the plate plane. These partial differential equations are changed to differential equations with respect only to the time t by using 2-D Fourier transform techniques.
- The displacement in the wavenumber domain is obtained by using a method of modal expansions.
- The displacement vector of the plate, \mathbf{d} , can finally be obtained by evaluating numerically the following 2-D inverse Fourier integration,

$$\mathbf{d}(x, y) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \tilde{\mathbf{d}}(k_x, k_y) e^{-ik_x x} e^{-ik_y y} dk_x dk_y . \quad (1)$$

In Eqn 1, k_x and k_y are the wave number with respect to x and y , and $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}$ is the displacement vector in the wave number domain, which depends on the time history of the external load. A time-step load is considered in this paper, because any other load of time history can be obtained by superposition of the results for the time-step load. For a time-step point load acting at $x=0$ and $y=0$, we have

$$\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{F}_0 \delta(x)\delta(y)H(t) , \quad (2)$$

where δ is the Dirac delta function, $H(t)$ is the Heaviside step function of time t , and \mathbf{F}_0 is a constant amplitude vector of the applied load. Following the procedure given by Liu et al.[15], we obtain

$$\tilde{\mathbf{d}} = \sum_{m=1}^M \Phi_m(k_x, k_y) (1 - \cos \omega_m t) = \sum_{m=1}^M \frac{\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^L \mathbf{F}_0 \boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^R}{\omega_m^2 (\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^L \mathbf{M}_t \boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^R)} (1 - \cos \omega_m t) , \quad (3)$$

where ω_m and $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^R$ are the m th angular eigen-frequency and corresponding right eigenvectors obtained from the following eigenvalue equations,

$$0 = [\mathbf{K}_t - \omega \mathbf{M}_t] \boldsymbol{\varphi}^R , \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{K}_t is the stiffness matrix given by

$$\mathbf{K}_t = k_x^2 \mathbf{A}_{1t} + k_x k_y \mathbf{A}_{2t} + k_y^2 \mathbf{A}_{3t} - ik_x \mathbf{A}_{4t} - ik_y \mathbf{A}_{5t} + \mathbf{A}_{6t} . \quad (5)$$

In equation (3), (4), and (5), the matrices \mathbf{A}_{it} , ($i=1, 6$) and \mathbf{M}_t can be found in the paper by Liu et al. [15]. It is found that \mathbf{K}_t is a Hermitian matrix, hence the left eigenvector $\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^L$ used in Eqn 3 can be obtained by

$$(\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^L)^T = (\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^R)^* , \quad (6)$$

where the superscript "T" stands for the transposed vector, and the asterisk denotes the complex conjugate.

A TECHNIQUE FOR EVALUATION OF INTEGRALS

Problems

The fast Fourier transform technique (FFT) has been used by Liu et al. [13-15] to evaluate the inverse integrations of Eqn 1. The FFT is very efficient for calculating whole field on a plane parallel to the plate plane, as shown by Liu et al. [15]. However, the disadvantage is that it requires a large number of sampling points on the wavenumber axes k_x and k_y , especially for long time and far field responses. The reason is that the kernel, $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}$, is a highly oscillatory function of k_x and k_y especially for large wave numbers and for large time t . Figure 2 is an example showing one component of the vibrating $\tilde{\mathbf{d}}$ for an hybrid laminated plate. From Eqn 1, it can be seen that the term $\exp[-i(k_x x + k_y y)]$ is also oscillatory, and the frequency of the oscillation is proportional to the observation distance x and/or y . Dealing with such a highly oscillatory integrand, a large number of sampling points has to be used if the FFT is

employed. To improve the efficiency and accuracy for evaluating the 2-D Fourier integration like Eqn 1, a much more efficient integrate technique is proposed as follows.

Solution to the problem

By introducing

$$k_x = k \cos \theta, \quad k_y = k \sin \theta, \quad (7)$$

where θ is the direction of a plane wave with a wavenumber of k , the integration in Eqn 1 is changed into the polar coordinate system:

$$d(x, y) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \tilde{D}(k, \theta) e^{-is} dk d\theta, \quad (8)$$

where

$$s = k(x \cos \theta + y \sin \theta), \quad (9)$$

$$\tilde{D} = \sum_{m=1}^M \Psi_m(k, \theta) (1 - \cos \omega_m t), \quad (10)$$

in which

$$\Psi_m = \frac{\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^L \mathbf{F}_{0t} \boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^R}{\omega_m^2 (\boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^L \mathbf{M}_t \boldsymbol{\varphi}_m^R)} k = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_m k. \quad (11)$$

The eigen-frequencies and the corresponding eigen-vectors can still be obtained from Eqn 4, but the stiffness matrix \mathbf{K}_t should be changed to

$$\mathbf{K}_t = k^2 (\cos^2 \theta \mathbf{A}_{1t} + \cos \theta \sin \theta \mathbf{A}_{2t} + \sin^2 \theta \mathbf{A}_{3t}) - ik (\cos \theta \mathbf{A}_{4t} + \sin \theta \mathbf{A}_{5t}) + \mathbf{A}_{6t}. \quad (12)$$

Rewriting from Eqn 1 to Eqn 8 does not change the important properties of the integral kernel, such as that the kernel frequently oscillates with respect to both k and θ . However, the double infinite integration in Eqn 1 is changed to be a double integration over a finite range for θ and semi-infinite range for k . This is more convenient for the numerical evaluation of the integration.

It can see from Eqn 10, that a kernel for a wave mode is a product of a modal factor function Ψ_m and a time related function $(1 - \cos \omega_m t)$. Modal factor function Ψ_m for the lowest ten wave modes in a hybrid laminated plate is calculated and shown in Fig.3. It is found that Ψ_m has the following features: (i). Function Ψ_m does not vibrate and vary rapidly except at the vicinity of origin, $k_x = 0$ and $k_y = 0$. (ii). For lowest modes, Ψ_m is singular at the origin, but for \tilde{D} this singular point is removable and \tilde{D} behaves well in the vicinity of the origin. Hence, the oscillating source is the function $(1 - \cos \omega_m t)$, and the frequency of the oscillation is proportional to the time t . It is also found that Ψ_m does not oscillate and vary rapidly with respect to θ , because Ψ_m depends only on the anisotropy of the material for a given k , and the material properties do not change very rapidly with θ . Moreover, it has been found [21] that ω_m does not vary rapidly with respect to k as well as θ . Taking advantages of the above-mentioned features of Ψ_m , ω_m and \tilde{D} , the inverse integration in Eqn 8 is handled by the following procedure.

First, the integration in Eqn 8 is divided into two parts:

$$d(x, y) = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\infty \tilde{D}(k, \theta) e^{-iks} dk d\theta = I_1 + I_2, \quad (13)$$

where d is any component of \mathbf{d} , \tilde{D} is the component of $\tilde{\mathbf{D}}$ corresponding to d , and

$$I_1 = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^{k_a} \tilde{D}(k, \theta) e^{-iks} dk d\theta, \quad (14)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
I_2 &= \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{k_a}^{\infty} \tilde{D}(k, \theta) e^{-is} dk d\theta \\
&= \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \sum_{m=1}^M \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{k_a}^{\infty} \Psi_m(k, \theta) (1 - \cos \omega_m t) e^{-is} dk d\theta = \frac{1}{4\pi^2} \sum_{m=1}^M I_{2m}
\end{aligned} \tag{15}$$

where k_a is a small number, so that I_1 can be carried out by using conventional even spaced quadrature routines. In dealing with I_2 , the integration is evaluated for each mode, and

$$I_{2m} \approx \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{k_a}^{k_b} \Psi_m(k, \theta) (1 - \cos \omega_m t) e^{-is} dk d\theta = I_{2m}^c - I_{2m}^t, \tag{16}$$

where k_b is a very large number where Ψ_m vanishes. The truncation error caused by cutting off the integration over k_b to ∞ will be discussed in the next section. Integration in Eqn 16 has been further divided into two parts. One is independent of time t , and another is dependent on t :

$$I_{2m}^c = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{k_a}^{k_b} \Psi_m(k, \theta) e^{-is} dk d\theta, \tag{17}$$

$$I_{2m}^t = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{k_a}^{k_b} \Psi_m(k, \theta) \cos(\omega_m t) e^{-is} dk d\theta. \tag{18}$$

As mentioned before, Ψ_m does not vary rapidly in the range of $k \geq k_a$ and $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$. Hence, we divide the region $k_a \leq k \leq k_b$ into $(L_k - 1)$ intervals:

$$k_a = k_1 < k_2 < \dots < k_j < \dots < k_{L_k} = k_b, \tag{19}$$

and divided the region $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$ into $(L_\theta - 1)$ even intervals:

$$0 = \theta_1 < \theta_2 < \dots < \theta_i < \dots < \theta_{L_\theta} = 2\pi. \tag{20}$$

For sufficiently large L_k and L_θ , Ψ_m , s and ω_m can be approximately replaced by a plane in each rectangular range of $k_i \leq k \leq k_{i+1}$ and $\theta_j \leq \theta \leq \theta_{j+1}$:

$$\Psi_{mij}(k, \theta) = a_{mij}^{(1)} \theta + a_{mij}^{(2)} k + a_{mij}^{(3)}, \tag{21}$$

$$s_{ij}(k, \theta) = b_{mij}^{(1)} \theta + b_{mij}^{(2)} k + b_{mij}^{(3)}, \tag{22}$$

$$\omega_{mij}(k, \theta) = c_{mij}^{(1)} \theta + c_{mij}^{(2)} k + c_{mij}^{(3)}, \tag{23}$$

where in Eqn 21, $a_{mij}^{(1)}$, $a_{mij}^{(2)}$ and $a_{mij}^{(3)}$ are determined by the following rules:

(i). The inclination of the plane with respect to θ equals to that of the line passing through two points of $(\frac{\Psi_{m,i,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i,j}}{2}, \theta_i)$ and $(\frac{\Psi_{m,i+1,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j}}{2}, \theta_{i+1})$, thus

$$a_{mij}^{(1)} = \frac{(\Psi_{m,i+1,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j}) - (\Psi_{m,i,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i,j})}{2(\theta_{i+1} - \theta_i)}. \tag{24}$$

(ii). The inclination of the plane with respect to k equals to that of the line passing through two points of $(\frac{\Psi_{m,i,j} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j}}{2}, k_j)$ and $(\frac{\Psi_{m,i,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j+1}}{2}, k_{j+1})$, we have

$$a_{mij}^{(2)} = \frac{(\Psi_{m,i,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j+1}) - (\Psi_{m,i,j} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j})}{2(k_{j+1} - k_j)}. \tag{25}$$

(iii). The plane passes through the point of $(\frac{\theta_{i+1} - \theta_i}{2}, \frac{k_{j+1} - k_j}{2})$,

$\frac{\Psi_{m,i,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i,j} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j}}{4}$), hence we obtain

$$a_{mij}^{(3)} = (\Psi_{m,i,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j+1} + \Psi_{m,i,j} + \Psi_{m,i+1,j}) / 4 - a_{mij}^{(1)}(\theta_{i+1} - \theta_i) - a_{mij}^{(2)}(k_{i+1} - k_i). \tag{26}$$

In Eqns 22 and 23, b_{mij} s, and c_{mij} s can be obtained by exactly the same way as obtaining a_{mij} s. Integrations in Eqns 17 and 18 can then be expressed as

$$I_{2m}^c = \sum_{i=1}^{L_a} \sum_{j=1}^{L_n} \int_{k_j}^{k_{j+1}} \int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_{i+1}} (a_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + a_{mij}^{(2)}k + a_{mij}^{(3)}) e^{-i(b_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + b_{mij}^{(2)}k + b_{mij}^{(3)})} dk d\theta$$

$$= \sum_{i=1}^{L_a} \sum_{j=1}^{L_n} I_{mij}^c \quad , \quad (27)$$

$$I_{2m}^t = \sum_{i=1}^{L_a} \sum_{j=1}^{L_n} \int_{k_j}^{k_{j+1}} \int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_{i+1}} (a_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + a_{mij}^{(2)}k + a_{mij}^{(3)}) \cos[(c_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + c_{mij}^{(2)}k + c_{mij}^{(3)})t]$$

$$\times e^{-i(b_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + b_{mij}^{(2)}k + b_{mij}^{(3)})} dk d\theta = \sum_{i=1}^{L_a} \sum_{j=1}^{L_n} I_{mij}^t \quad . \quad (28)$$

The integrations I_{mij}^c and I_{mij}^t in Eqns 27 and 28 can then be carried out analytically.

For general anisotropic materials, Ψ_m is complex valued, and a complex integration for Eqn 8 have to be evaluated. However, for anisotropic materials of 13 independent constants, the Hermitian stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} can be changed to a real symmetrical one²², and hence Ψ_m can be real. Fiber reinforced laminated plates falls into the case if the fiber is laid in the plate plane. Therefore, the integration can be done in real number. The equations have been derived and listed as follows:

(i). For loads in the z direction, to obtain displacement components in x direction, u , and in y direction, v , or for load in either x or y direction, to obtain the displacement component in z direction, w , the integration in Eqns 27 and 28 are changed to be

$$I_{mij}^c = \int_{k_j}^{k_{j+1}} \int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_{i+1}} (a_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + a_{mij}^{(2)}k + a_{mij}^{(3)}) \sin(b_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + b_{mij}^{(2)}k + b_{mij}^{(3)}) dk d\theta \quad , \quad (29)$$

$$I_{2m}^t = \frac{1}{2} \int_{k_j}^{k_{j+1}} \int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_{i+1}} (a_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + a_{mij}^{(2)}k + a_{mij}^{(3)})$$

$$\times \{ \sin[(c_{mij}^{(1)}t + b_{mij}^{(1)})\theta + (c_{mij}^{(2)}t + b_{mij}^{(2)})k + (c_{mij}^{(3)}t + b_{mij}^{(3)})] \\ - \sin[(c_{mij}^{(1)}t - b_{mij}^{(1)})\theta + (c_{mij}^{(2)}t - b_{mij}^{(2)})k + (c_{mij}^{(3)}t - b_{mij}^{(3)})] \} dk d\theta \quad . \quad (30)$$

(ii). For loads in the z direction, to obtain displacement components in z direction, w , or for load in either x or y direction, to obtain the displacement components in x direction, u , and in y direction, v , the integration in Eqns 27 and 28 are given by

$$I_{mij}^c = \int_{k_j}^{k_{j+1}} \int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_{i+1}} (a_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + a_{mij}^{(2)}k + a_{mij}^{(3)}) \cos(b_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + b_{mij}^{(2)}k + b_{mij}^{(3)}) dk d\theta \quad , \quad (31)$$

$$I_{2m}^t = \frac{1}{2} \int_{k_j}^{k_{j+1}} \int_{\theta_i}^{\theta_{i+1}} (a_{mij}^{(1)}\theta + a_{mij}^{(2)}k + a_{mij}^{(3)})$$

$$\times \{ \cos[(c_{mij}^{(1)}t + b_{mij}^{(1)})\theta + (c_{mij}^{(2)}t + b_{mij}^{(2)})k + (c_{mij}^{(3)}t + b_{mij}^{(3)})] \\ + \cos[(c_{mij}^{(1)}t - b_{mij}^{(1)})\theta + (c_{mij}^{(2)}t - b_{mij}^{(2)})k + (c_{mij}^{(3)}t - b_{mij}^{(3)})] \} dk d\theta \quad . \quad (32)$$

Again, the integrations in Eqns 29-32 can be carried out analytically, and easily implemented into a program.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

The new technique has been implemented into the 3-D HNM program. Responses of an isotropic plate loaded on the upper surface are computed by the modified HNM program. The results are compared with those obtained by an exact method. Responses of a hybrid laminated plate denoted by [C90/G+45/G-45]_s subjected to point loads on the upper surface of

the plate is computed by both the original and modified HNM. The time histories of the loads are the time-step and one cycle of a sine function. In the notation for the laminate, the letters C and G stand respectively, for carbon/epoxy and glass/epoxy layers, while the numbers following the letters indicate the angle of the fiber-orientation with respect to the x axis. The subscript s indicates that the plate is symmetrically stacked. Hence the plate is actually made of six layers. The Poisson's ratio of the material for the isotropic plate is 0.25. The material constants for the hybrid laminated plate given in Table 1 in Ref. 21.

In this paper, the following dimensionless parameters are used.

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{x} &= x / H, \quad \bar{y} = y / H, \quad \bar{w} = \mathbf{c}(4,4)w / q_0, \quad \bar{u}_r = \mathbf{c}(4,4)u_r / q_0, \\ \bar{\omega} &= \omega H / c_s, \quad \bar{t} = t c_s / H, \quad c_s = \sqrt{\mathbf{c}(4,4) / \rho}, \end{aligned} \quad (33)$$

where w and u_r are, respectively, the displacements in the z direction and radial direction in the x - y plane, and \mathbf{c} , ρ , and c_s are the material constants matrix, density, and shear wave velocity of a reference material. For the isotropic plate, the reference material is the material of the plate. For the hybrid laminated plate, the reference material is the C90.

Figure 4 shows the time history of the displacement w on the surface of the isotropic plate subjected to a time-step point load. The load is on the upper surface at $x = 0$ and $y=0$, and in the thickness direction of the plate. The observation position is at $x=4.0H$, and $y=0$. The dotted line is obtained by the present modified HNM, and the solid line is obtained by the method of generalized rays, an exact method⁵. In the HNM, the integration for θ is needed to be done only over 0 to $\pi/2$, due to the isotropy of the material. In the HNM, twelve elements, and twenty modes have been used. Parameters used in Eqns 15 and 17 are $k_a = \pi$, and $k_b = 11\pi$. The sampling points needed in the modified HNM is 70 for k and 51 for θ or 3570 in total. The original HNM program has also used for the same computation, and the sampling points are 512 for both k_x and k_y or 262144 in total to get the same accuracy of results. This is about 70 times of the sampling point needed for the modified HNM.

From Fig.4 differences between results obtained by the HNM and the exact method can be observed. Errors in the results by the HNM are caused by three reasons: the number of the elements N , the number of mode M , and truncating point k_b . As a time-step load is considered, the exciting source contains frequencies of infinity. On the other hand, due to the nature of the HNM, it cannot take infinity frequencies into account, even though using larger N , M , and/or k_b will get better results. However, the purpose to obtain the responses for the time-step load is to obtain responses for a load of any time history. For a practical case, the frequency of a load is finite, and hence the HNM is useful for these kind of loads. The results for a load of any time-history can be obtained from results for the time-step load by the following equation.

$$d(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{L_t} [d^H(t-\tau_i) - d^H(t-\tau_{i+1})] f\left(\frac{\tau_{i+1} + \tau_i}{2}\right), \quad (34)$$

where the superscript "H" stands for results for the time-step load, and

$$0 = \tau_1 < \tau_2 < \dots < \tau_i < \dots < \tau_{L_t} = t_d, \quad (35)$$

where t_d is the duration of the load with a time history function f .

To prove this, we consider a load with a time history function of

$$f(t) = \sin(2\pi t / t_d), \quad 0 < t < t_d. \quad (36)$$

The frequency spectrum for $\bar{t}_d = 2.0$ are shown in Fig.5. Responses of the vertical displacement on the upper surface of the isotropic plate subjected to the point load with a time history of Eqn 36 are computed by the modified HNM, and results are shown in Fig.6. The load acts in the vertical direction and on the upper surface at $x = 0$ and $y = 0$. The solid line is

obtained by using $N = 12$, $M = 20$ and $k_b = 11\pi$, and the dotted line is obtained by doubling these parameters, that is $N = 24$, $M = 40$ and $k_b = 22\pi$. However, these two curves are almost coincident, and hardly to be distinguished. The reasons are as follows. From Fig.5, it is found that the components with a dimensionless frequency higher than 15.0 are very small. Therefore the highest frequency is considered to be approximately 15.0. At this highest frequency, the wave length of the shear wave in the material of the plate is about $0.42H$. For this frequency, $N = 12$, $M = 20$ and $k_b = 11\pi$ is sufficient to obtain good results, because the thickness of one element is far less than a quarter of the shear wave length, and frequencies for modes higher than 20 and for $k > k_b$ are higher than the highest frequency of the load.

COMMENTS AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a technique is presented to modify the original HNM to compute 3-D responses of anisotropic laminated plate subjected to time-step point load. It is found that the modal factor functions and eigen-frequencies behave very well, and only a small number of sampling point is needed to get very good results numerically. Also because only modal factor functions and eigen-frequencies, which are only related to the properties of the plate, are replaced by piece wise planes, the replacement can be used to obtain the results for all the different observation locations and times. This, therefore, saves the computation of the modal factor functions and eigen-frequencies, when lots of observation locations and times are required. The advantages of the techniques proposed for the modified HNM are summarized as follow:

- This technique can significantly reduce sampling points in evaluating the inverse Fourier transform integrations to obtain 3-D transient responses of anisotropic laminated plates subjected to time-step point loads.
- The number of the sampling points does not increase as the observation time increases. Hence the modified HNM can be used to obtain long time responses.
- The number of the sampling points does not increase as the observation distance increases. Hence the modified HNM can be used to obtain far field responses.

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Fig.1 An anisotropic laminated plate and its coordinate system

Fig.2 Displacement w in wave number domain on the upper surface for plate $[C90/G+45/G-45]_S$ subjected to a time-step vertical point load on the upper surface of the plate ($\bar{t} = 20.0, k_y H = 1.0$).

Fig.3 Lowest 10 modal factor functions for displacement w on the upper surface for plate $[C90/G+45/G-45]_S$ ($\theta = \pi/4$).

Fig. 4 Time histories of the vertical displacement w at $x = 4H$ on the upper surface of an isotropic plate subjected to a time-step point load acting on the upper surface at $x = 0, y = 0$. The dotted line is obtained by the present technique, and the solid line is obtained by an exact method⁵.

Fig. 6 Time histories of the vertical displacement w at $x = 4H$ on the upper surface of the plate $[C90/G+45/G-45]_S$ subjected to a point load acting on the upper surface at $x = 0, y = 0$. The time history of the load is given by Eqn 36 ($\bar{t}_d = 2.0$). The dotted line: $N = 24, M = 40$ and $k_b = 22\pi$. Solid line: $N = 12, M = 20$ and $k_b = 11\pi$.